

deformed sheet .The strain-hardening characteristic of sheet metal is assumed to follow the form:

$$\bar{\sigma} = K\bar{\epsilon}^n \quad (1)$$

III. FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION

There are numerous influencing parameters, but according to the experimental and simulation results, the primary ones are punch radius (r_1), die radius(r_2), die arc radius (r_d), friction coefficient (m), thickness (t_0), yield strength of sheet (σ_y) and strain hardening exponent (K, n) Through 20 sets of finite element analysis under different working condition the input data achieved (Table.1). At the same time in order to confirm the validity of the neural network model, an extra three simulation are carried out under different condition from the above 20 sets (Table.2).

Because of the existing symmetry, only one quarter of the workpiece is considered in the modeling (Fig.2). The tooling surface of die was modeled using rigid- body model. Simulations were carried out from the sheet of diameter 100 mm with the diameter progressively increasing by 5 mm until the sheet was fractured.

Compares the LDR value obtained by FEM simulation with that obtained experimentally [4], proving that the model proposed herein is accurate in determining the LDR of deep drawing process.

Fig.2 FEM simulation

IV. NEURAL NETWORKS

An artificial neural network is a parallel distributed information processing system. It stores the samples with distributed coding, thus forming a trainable nonlinear system. The main idea behind a neural network approach resembles the human brain functioning. Given the input and the expected outputs, the program is self adaptive to the environment so as to respond to different inputs rationally. The objective of this paper is to investigate the prediction of LDR in deep drawing process, by training a BPANN.

The neuron can be classified into three types: input, output, hidden neurons. Input neurons are the ones that receive input from the environment, such as punch radius (r_1), die radius(r_2), die arc radius (r_d), friction coefficient (m), thickness (t_0), yield

strength of sheet (σ_y) and strain hardening exponent (K, n) in this study. Output neurons are those that send the signals out of the system, like LDR. As the activation function, Sig activation function has been used, which is continuous, nonlinear, monotonic non-decreasing and S shaped function (equation 2). [5]

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\beta x}} \quad (2)$$

In this study, the back propagation, which is a widely used algorithm, is used in the training step. Back propagation is a systematic method for training multilayer artificial neural networks. It has a strong mathematical foundation based on gradient descent learning. Elman BP network train with the back propagation algorithm is used. Elman networks are back propagation networks, with the addition of a feedback connection from the output of the hidden layer to its input. This feedback path allows Elman networks to learn to recognize and generate temporal patterns, as well as spatial patterns [6]. For an Elman to have the best chance at learning a problem it needs more hidden neurons in its hidden layer than are actually required for a solution by another method.

This model has four layers including, an input layer, two hidden layer and an output layer. In this work, different number of hidden units has been employed to obtain the optimum number of hidden units. The experiments show that number of 12 units in the hidden layer is enough to reach the desired accuracy (Table.3).

Training of the neural network was done in MATLAB, using Sig and TRAINLM function. TRAINLM is a network training function that updates weights and bias values in a back propagation algorithm according to Levenberg–Marquardt optimization. Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm is a highly efficient method for solving non-linear optimization problems [7], [8]. The trained network model showed error of 1.9%, 3.15% and 7.4% while testing with the 3 data sets (Table. 2).

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, a four-layer back propagation network is developed to best fit this nonlinear engineering problem. Through comparison between the targeted value and training results with different neuron numbers in the hidden layers, an appropriate number of 12 is suitable to set up this network. For this nonlinear engineering problem, the appropriate algorithm is Levenberg -Marquardt because it can reach high accuracy. The error between the predicted value and targeted one is little. Using this network can save much time

TABLE I
 FEM SIMULATION CONDITION

	punch radius (r_1) mm	die arc radius (r_d) mm	die radius (r_2) mm	friction coefficient (μ)	thickness (t_0) mm	yield strength (σ_y) Mpa	k	n	(LDR)
1	30.75	8.5	39.25	0.1	1	155	610	0.263	2.13
2	30.75	8.5	39.25	0.2	1	155	610	0.263	2.11
3	30.75	8.5	39.25	0.1	1	157	612	0.248	2.13
4	30.75	8.5	39.25	0.2	1	157	612	0.248	2.10
5	30.65	8.6	39.25	0.1	1.2	138	619	0.264	2.20
6	30.78	8.6	39.38	0.1	1.2	138	619	0.264	2.22
7	30.78	8.6	39.38	0.2	1.2	138	619	0.264	2.16
8	30.86	8.6	39.46	0.1	1.2	138	619	0.264	2.12
9	30.86	8.6	39.46	0.2	1.2	138	619	0.264	2.09
10	30.86	5.4	39.26	0.2	1.2	171	622	0.228	2.03
11	30.86	8.6	39.25	0.2	1.2	171	622	0.228	2.07
12	30.86	10.6	41.46	0.2	1.2	171	622	0.228	2.08
13	30.86	12.6	43.46	0.2	1.2	171	622	0.228	2.12
14	30.86	14.6	45.46	0.2	1.2	171	622	0.228	2.15
15	26.48	6.79	33.27	0.05	0.88	258	631	0.238	2.40
16	26.52	6.74	33.27	0.05	0.79	203	631	0.238	2.43
17	26.55	6.71	33.27	0.05	0.73	300	631	0.238	2.37
18	26.55	6.71	33.27	0.05	0.73	292	631	0.238	2.39
19	26.25	6.84	33.27	0.05	0.99	276	631	0.238	2.36
20	26.42	6.85	33.24	0.05	1	244	631	0.238	2.33

TABLE II
 TEST CONDITION

	punch radius (r_1) mm	die arc radius (r_d) mm	die radius (r_2) mm	friction coefficient (μ)	thickness (t_0) mm	k	n	yield strength (σ_y) Mpa
1	30.65	8.6	39.25	0.2	1.2	619	0.264	138
2	26.47	6.80	33.27	0.05	0.90	631	0.238	202
3	30.75	8.5	39.25	0.15	1	610	0.262	155

Fig.3 The structure of the neural network

TABLE III
 COMPARISON OF MEAN SQUARE ERROR USING DIFFERENT
 STRUCTURE OF ANN

Structure of ANN	MSE Mean square error
8-6-6-1	17712e-6
8-7-7-1	14230e-8
8-8-8-1	45483e-10
8-9-9-1	14193e-11
8-10-10-1	16177e-6
8-11-11-1	16502e-12
8-12-12-1	26958e-13
8-13-13-1	14833e-6
8-14-14-1	13131e-6

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